

APPRAISAL ANALYSIS TO DESIGN PROCESS: A CASE STUDY ON EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the possibility, through an appraisals analysis, to qualify the experience of candidates for Master's degrees in order to reduce their anxiety when it comes to choosing these programs. Using a theoretical and methodological approach based on Appraisals Theory, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 people (interested in applying to Master's in different areas), who reported anxiety when choosing their programs. Based on empirical results, it was possible to identify categories that were explored through the relationship with this theory. This analysis brought elements that have provided support for generating design guidelines in order to qualify the experiences of future Master's degree students.

KEYWORDS: *design process; design and emotion; emotional experience; appraisals theory; education.*

INTRODUCTION

The higher education scene in Brazil has shown an increasing number of graduate programs. This growth, however, brings challenges for higher education institutions that are seeking to attract students and secure a better position against their competitors. One way to attract new students is to qualify the applicant's experience. The *Design for Emotion* field, which is in focus of this short paper, aims to design products and services with the explicit intention of evoking or preventing certain emotions, so it can be easily related to the need for universities to qualify the experience of future students.

Among the different theoretical and methodological approaches to design for emotions, Appraisals Theory states that an emotion is the result of a person's appraisal regarding the potential effect of a stimulus on his or her welfare (Demir, Desmet and Hekkert, 2009). Based on this context, this study examines how it is possible, through an appraisal analysis, to qualify the experience of candidates for Master's degrees in order to prevent anxiety when it comes to choosing a course. It is important to emphasize that the focus is not career selection but the information seeking process, which is why the case study focuses on the stage of data collection with future candidates for a Master's program.

Although anxiety is an important point of this study, the authors did not intend to theoretically explore it in this short paper. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that anxiety is commonly defined as an experience of fear and apprehension regarding an anticipation of potential danger, whether this is real or imagined (CASTILLO et al., 2000). The main reason for this choice (anxiety) is given by the results found in this study (explored in the "Results and Discussion" section). These results are based on the respondents' appraisals, which indicated anxiety as one of the common emotions evoked during the information seeking process for Master's courses. This analysis, therefore, resulted in an understanding that emotions and their causes can generate design stimuli that can help us to understand how to avoid anxiety among these students.

METHODS

The study had a qualitative approach, and fourteen in-depth interviews were conducted with people who applied for Master's courses. Participants were recruited during the application process for Master's courses at several Brazilian universities. They were accessed through these universities, which provided their e-mail addresses.

The authors contacted seventy-eight students who were in the information seeking process, in an estimated period of 30 days prior to the formalization of program enrolment. Twenty people answered the e-mails and were then sent a second e-mail, including a list of emotions as stimulus (Scherer, 2005). They were asked to indicate which of those emotions were experienced during the information seeking process. Since anxiety was mentioned by all participants, the authors have focused on conducting in-depth interviews only with those who did report it. Fourteen applicants participated in this stage.

A script to be used for data collection was adapted from Demir et al. (2009) considering issues related to the interaction of the users with services (not products). Data collection included the following steps:

- The participants received a word list of emotions based on Scherer's list (2005) and they selected three emotions. To raise awareness and familiarize themselves with the process of reporting their emotions, participants were asked to report experiences related to three emotions referred by them.
- An in-depth interview was conducted, focusing on the anxiety reported during the information seeking process of applying to a Master's course.
- The script for in-depth interviews followed the componential model of appraisals, which included seven questions to reflect the essence of the seven appraisal components (Demir et al, 2009): (1) During the information seeking process, did you achieve your goals? (Motive Consistency), (2) How enjoyable was this process? (Intrinsic pleasure), (3) How do you compare this process with others that you experienced in searching for information on other courses

and/or universities? (Standards conformance), (4) How does the information you found match (or not) your expectations? (Expectation confirmation), (5) How sure were you that the information you found is all you needed to know in terms of the future about these courses? (Certainty), (6) Whom, what event or what situation is responsible for potential hardships encountered in the process? (Agency), (7) How did you manage (or not) to deal with such adversity? (Coping potential). The aim of this script was to identify possible causes for anxiety (appraisals).

The average length of the interviews was 30 minutes. They were tape recorded for further scrutiny and Content Analysis. The data analysis was performed following the categorical analysis (Bardin, 1995), reorganizing the text by units. The process is defined by Moraes (1999) as categorization, since data were grouped according to what is common among them. After structuring results, it was possible to relate the categories (results) with the seven appraisal components (Demir et al., 2009). The results are presented in the next section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows results at two levels: (a) the first two columns indicate the categories and subcategories, respectively, indicating the essence of the contents verbalized by respondents, but not related to any theoretical elements, (b) the other columns show the relationships between empirical results and theoretical components of appraisals. The words highlighted in red show the negative reviews provided by participants, in which they mention anxiety in their experience. The words highlighted in blue show the positive reviews.

	CATEGORIES AND SUBCATEGORIES	MOTIVE CONSISTENCY	INTRINSIC PLEASURE	EXPECTATIONS CONFIRMATION	AGENCY	STANDARDS CONFORMANCE	CERTAINTY	COPING POTENTIAL
INFORMATION	Unknown information	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	Own candidate	---	Uncertainty	Low
	Level of clarity/ Lack of information	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	Information sender	---	Uncertainty	Low
PROFESSIONAL RESOURCES	Website	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	Information sender	Not Conformance	Uncertainty	Low
	Secretary attendance	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Information sender	Not Conformance	Certainty	High
	Professor attendance	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Information sender	Not Conformance	Certainty	High
	E-mail and phone attendance	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Information sender	Conformance	Certainty	High
NON-PROFESSIONAL RESOURCES	Own resources	Inconsistent	---	Expectation break down	Own candidate	---	Uncertainty	Low
	University location	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	The university	Conformance	Uncertainty	Low
	Contact other people	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Reference people	---	Certainty	High

Table 1. Relation of Categories x Appraisals Components

Source: Authors (2013)

The “information” category was divided into two subcategories. First, unknown information was related to the real goals of a Master's degree, which should, according to the respondents, be demystified and better explained by higher education institutions offering courses at that level. The participants addressed this point by referencing the fact that they had no knowledge of what a Master's degree level can offer or ignorance in terms of what will occur after completion of the course. Second, lack of information is related to the understanding of what is offered by a Master's program. This subcategory was created according to the testimony of respondents who expressed anxiety for not understanding the information provided or demanded more complete information. In other words, the knowledge exists, but there is no confirmation of that. Consequently, anxiety was related to inconsistent reasons, not confirming expectations, various agencies, uncertainties and low coping potential.

The “professional resources” category involves people and sources of information that interested parties have sought in an attempt to answer their questions. These are organized into four subcategories. First, the information seeking process through the university website, is related to inconsistent reasons, expectation disconfirmation, agency (information sender), non-confirmation of standards, uncertainty and low coping potential. The second and third subcategories are related to each other in the sense that they represent face-to-face forms of interaction between applicants and university representatives. The fourth subcategory is related to email and telephone interaction of secretarial staff. The relationship of these three subcategories with the appraisal components showed that anxiety can be prevented through consistent motives, confirmation of expectations, certainties and high coping potential. However, for standards conformance, we observed reduced anxiety only through non-personal interaction, unlike the subcategories of the secretarial staff and professor attendance, in which there was anxiety related to non-compliant standards.

The “non-professional resources” category involves other information channels and/or forms through which stakeholders seek information to deal with situations that could generate negative emotions during the application process. This category is organized into three subcategories: own resources of applicants to deal with problems, the location of the university, and relationship and contact with other people.

In the “own resources” sub-category, one can say that each individual creates his or her own way to deal with the anxiety evoked by the process of looking for information and deciding. Negative results may arise if the person, after feeling anxious, decides not to look for information. Also, negative results may arise if the person does not look for information through the other channels, like those mentioned above. Thus, uncertainty and anxiety may develop substantially if the applicant does not know how to deal with such issues. Some participants mentioned the “location of university” as a cause of anxiety, even though it is not considered a resource that is managed by applicants during the information seeking process. Relating these two sub-components with the appraisals, we can see

that the triggers for anxiety can be inconsistent, no confirmation and break-down of expectations, agencies (the applicant and the university become responsible), uncertainties and low potential for coping.

The last subcategory, “relations and contact with other people” is related to the personal contacts that applicants have and use in order to deal with anxiety. These people play an important role because they use words of encouragement and help to clarify what a Master's course means and implies for the applicant's life. In this case, this subcategory shows that anxiety can be reduced if facing a consistent motive, confirming expectations, agency (who are people who serve as reference for applicants), certainty and a high coping potential.

CONCLUSION

The results provide insights for future design processes. According to Desmet and Hekkert (2009), understanding the emotions of users resulting from the interaction with a product or service can help the designer visualize, in advance, possible ways to avoid negative outcomes.

In this case, it was necessary, in addition to understanding the role of anxiety in this process, to comprehend the appraisals that lead to it. Exploring these causes, based on the evaluation components of Appraisal Theory, provides a better understanding of cause-effect relationships (design-anxiety), highlighting tangible elements to support the design process. Such comprehension, therefore, is important for discussion and understanding of ways that may serve as stimuli to designers when it comes to developing services.

Results from Table 1 showed that design for emotion, applied in the context of higher education services, has the potential to develop interventions that may reduce the anxiety experienced in the information seeking process of Master's courses. The following design inputs are provided:

- a) Regarding the level of clarity and lack of information about courses, it is important to design consistent ways of providing information, considering the user's actual doubts and level of comprehension.
- b) Designing websites that facilitate access to clearer information and that may allow that may allow for controlled changed to be made by the users, following their language and understanding of the intended courses.
- c) The designer may use different elements of assistance from the secretarial staff and professors explored by users and so design artefacts that exceed the desired pattern and reduce anxiety.
- d) The location of the university and applicants' own resources are elements that are not easily controlled by designers. However, professionals can design methods that contribute to increasing applicants' awareness of universities' predetermined rules in order to cope with the anxiety caused by this situation.

- e) The category involving people that serve as a reference showed that they contribute positively to the information seeking process. In this case, it is clear that not all causes of anxiety in choosing a course are easily controllable by design, since it may be difficult to manage these people serving as reference.

Thus, future studies could help develop projects based on the aforementioned guidelines, which have the potential to reduce the anxiety of prospective students who want to apply for a Master's degree.

REFERENCES

- BARDIN, Laurence. (1995) *Análise de Conteúdo*. Lisboa: Edições 70.
- CASTILLO, A.R. G. L.; ASBAHR, F. R.; MANFRO, G.G. (2000) Transtornos de ansiedade. *Revista Brasileira Psiquiatria*, vol. 22, n. 2.
- DEMIR, E.; DESMET, P. M. A.; HEKKERT, P. (2009) Appraisal Patterns of Emotions in Human-Product Interaction. *International Journal of Design*. vol.3, n.2.
- DESMET, P. (2002). *Designing emotions*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands.
- DESMET, P.; HEKKERT, P. (2009) Special Issue Editorial: Design & Emotion. *Internacional Journal of Design*, vol.3, n.2.
- MORAES, Roque. (1999) *Análise de conteúdo*. *Revista Educação*, vol.22, n.37.
- SCHERER, K. R. (2005) What are emotions? And how can they be measured? *Social Science Information*, vol.44, n.4.